

Developing climate and emergency risk management strategy using state of the art benchmark for Târgu Secuiesc municipality to increase regional climate resilience (KÉZDI_adapt)

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Introduction

Târgu Secuiesc municipality is a micro-regional economic hub in Covasna County (RO) with a population of 17,000, is committed to enhancing climate resilience as a key to sustainable development. Our micro-region spans 42.86 km², of which 64% (27.55 km²) is farmland, 15% (6.61 km²) is pasture, and only 20% (8.7 km²) is urban settlement. Thus 79% of the total area is dedicated for agricultural activities, this sector plays a vital societal role—supporting livelihoods, providing resources, and driving local economies. However, these benefits are highly vulnerable to climate risks.

Specific objectives of KÉZDI_adapt project:

- ▶ Evaluation of impact regarding agricultural drought and river floods on agricultural and other land cover types and built environment;
- ▶ Increasing awareness of the importance of climate change impact on key community systems on micro-region level;
- ▶ Support SME's, local and national authorities on climate hazard types, expected damages, exposer and vulnerability.

Materials and methods

River flood workflow

The river floods workflow was assessed by using common information already available as high resolution JRD flood hazard maps, LUISA land cover dataset, and Damage Scanner tools. Two RCP scenarios 4.5 and 8.5, different return periods were applied (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75, 100, 200, 500) using specific bbox coordinates for our municipality.

Agricultural drought workflow

Studied crops: maize, wheat, potato, rapeseed which are intensively cultivated. Climate scenarios of RCP 2.6, 4.5, and 8.5 were analyzed, using start and end year periods as near future 2026–2030 and mid-century 2046–2050-time intervals. Crop specific parameters needed for hazard assessment were imported from the crop table selecting sub continental climate zone no. 5. Code extension helped to plot in more detail our interested region and additional layers of Administrative divisions increased the clarity of hazard and risk results plots.

Table 1. Data overview of workflows

Hazard data	Vulnerability data	Exposure data	Risk output
Agricultural drought	Aggregated crops revenue loss	Total crop production, crop yield loss	Map revenue loss
River floods	vulnerability damage curves	Land use	Map of flood depth and damage

Future work

The team will collect and analyse existing data to enhance the local accuracy of Phase 1 results, municipal orthophotos will be integrated with other GIS layers (agriculture, river basins, vegetation) from various databases. In the following Phase 3 the local applicability of the RAST adaptation strategy will be assessed to identify climate risks affecting key community systems. It will support the development of a practical climate adaptation and mitigation plan for Târgu Secuiesc, in strong collaboration with the County Emergency Inspectorate and other stakeholders (e.g. critical infrastructure, water supply, local farmers).

Results

River flood

Under RCP 8.5, flood damage escalates rapidly, with agricultural lands more vulnerable than residential areas. Longer Return Periods resulted in a larger flooded area in both examined scenarios. River flood risks worsen under RCP 8.5, with higher and faster damage rates. Data limitations affect long-term flood risk assessments, requiring improved modelling and flood protection integration.

Flood Hazard Data Limitations due to dataset covering only large river basins (>150 km²) and the lack of flood protection data causes inaccuracies. In case of 250-Year Return Period, data limitations generate unreliable flood maps, for distant projections.

Agricultural drought

Table 2. Average Yield loss (%) values NUTS2 region for different RCP climate change scenarios

RCP/Crop	RCP 2.6 RCP 4.5 RCP 8.5			RCP 2.6 RCP 4.5 RCP 8.5			ΔRCP 2.6 (%)	ΔRCP 4.5 (%)	ΔRCP 8.5 (%)				
	(2026-2030)			(2046-2050)									
Maize	38.433	⇒ 44.507	↑	29.899	⇒ 39.015	↓	37.561	↓	40.032	↑	0.582	-6.946	10.133
Wheat	21.122	⇒ 22.567	↑	25.218	⇒ 25.908	↓	20.799	↓	20.622	↓	4.786	-1.768	-4.596
Potato	31.866	⇒ 35.068	↑	26.124	⇒ 31.131	↓	31.032	↓	32.355	↑	-0.735	-4.036	6.231
Rapeseed	19.766	⇒ 21.751	↑	21.524	⇒ 27.303	↓	24.742	↓	22.382	↓	7.537	2.991	0.858

Potato ▶ remains financially stable with constant maximum loss for all scenarios; Maize ▶ has equal max. revenue loss (0.56) under RCP 2.6 and 4.5, increases to 0.54 under RCP 8.5; Wheat ▶ has higher losses in 2046-2050 (320) across all RCPs compared to 2026-2030 (280 under RCP 4.5, 8.5); Rapeseed ▶ Loss increases in 2046-2050 under RCP 8.5 (640) but stabilizes at 560 for RCP 2.6 & 4.5. Agriculture faces significant risks under extreme climate scenarios, particularly for maize and rapeseed, while potato remains the most resilient.

Table 3. Maximum revenue loss without irrigation for investigated periods

Revenue loss without irrigation (1000 EUR) 2026-2030				
RCP	Maize	Wheat	Potato	Rapeseed
2.6	0.56	320	48	640
4.5	0.56	280	48	560
8.5	0.64	280	48	640
Revenue loss without irrigation (1000 EUR) 2046-2050				
RCP	Maize	Wheat	Potato	Rapeseed
2.6	0.56	320	48	560
4.5	0.56	320	48	560
8.5	0.64	320	48	640

Main challenges:

Agricultural drought ▶ quantifying economic losses from climate impacts due to incomplete or missing climate and mostly irrigation datasets.

River flood ▶ limited access to high resolution models tailored to our region.

